

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Juraquliy Gulnoza Rustam qizi

Master student of SamSIFL

Abstract: The article is devoted to the review of the communicative approach in practice teaching english as a foreign language. The purpose of the communicative approach is to teach how to do using the studied foreign language as a means of constructive communication depending on the goals and communication goals, participants, and communication status.

Key words: Communicative approach, activity, game, learning language, classroom, temperament, ability, life experience, worldview.

Communicative language teaching (CLT) is also called communicative approach, which refers to teaching language through communication. This approach to language teaching creates a communication framework as a goal and method for english language learners whose first language is not english.

The essence of the communicative approach is that the teacher in the classroom a models of foreign language learning situations that help students acquire knowledge and skills, different types of speech activity. Skills and habits are formed in activities using only the necessary tools and in a certain environment. In this case, the concept of “activity” can be considered as purposeful actions motivated by units of life and culture under certain circumstances with different goals in mind. Looking different relations are formed in the conditions existing in a certain environment. Speech communication can be organized through dialogues on various topics, problem dialogues. This is necessary to teach speech by creating conditions for live speech communication in the classroom.

In the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account the personal qualities of students:

- Temperament,

- ability,
- life experience,
- worldview.

Communicative motivation plays an important role in the process of teaching english as a foreign language. Communicative motivation includes students' satisfaction as a result of use languages as a means of communication. If motivation remains at a sufficiently high level. The classroom environment is friendly, the relationships within the group and between the teacher and the teacher and students respect.

An important factor in ensuring communicative motivation is a role-playing game. Game allows effectively stimulate the activity of students of any age. Maintains interest communicating in a foreign language expands the subject content of the language being studied it is possible to go beyond the limited sphere of activity, allows you to expand your limits experience by playing the roles of people of different professions and personalities.

When teaching communicative language, priority is given to the development of students' communication and interaction skills. It ensures that students communicate effectively and confidently in real-life situations through student-student-teacher interactions. CLT mainly focuses on students learning a new language by using language to communicate with others around them.

Characteristics of the communicative approach

The communicative language teaching approach has various features, including the integration of reading, writing and speaking. For example, a teacher can ask students to watch a video and then write a couple of sentences about the video on the board. Students then read each other's thoughts and discuss how they felt about what they watched. It allows the application of several skills at the same time, which enables the learner to communicate effectively with others.

CLT also uses groups or pairs for activities that allow for collaboration in the language learning classroom. Working in groups or in pairs allows students to

discuss, practice and master the material without feeling alone in the process of learning a new language. Often working together, students feel comfortable practicing fluency over mistakes they make in their grammar. It ensures that students are on their way to fluency in a new language through collaboration where they can learn from each other and work together .

The communicative approach uses tools and technologies for a personalized learning approach. Every student learns differently and has different interests, so through clt teachers can individualize learning to meet the needs of their students. For example, students may like to talk about sports or popular culture, so a teacher can ask students to discuss these areas with each other through several activities, such as role-playing playing real-life scenarios, group discussion or pair discussion, and various other activities encourage collaboration.

Examples of communicative approach activities in the classroom

Role play is an effective activity often used in the clt classroom. For example, some students may like to shop, so the teacher decides that they should discuss their love of shopping through a role play. Does. One student acts as a cashier and the other as a customer. Through this role-playing game, two students can act out a conversation they would often hear between cashiers and customers in real life, such as what the weather is like, their how their day is going, what brings them to the store and so much more.

Interviews are also a great way to use clt in the classroom. For example, students can be put into groups and ask each other about their interests, such as what hobbies they like. Then the teacher gives brief information about the favorite activity of another student and why it is a favorite activity, asking each peer may be asked to convey the information they have learned. It allows students to repeat what they have heard but to work in informal, low-level collaboration where they do not feel like they are learning independently.

Group discussions and pair discussions are effective ways of prioritizing student interaction, which creates a more open and safe environment. While students

are listening to a teacher's lecture, if they are asked to put their skills into practice, for example through a group discussion, they may not retain this information. When students point out their own mistakes, such as grammar mistakes on a worksheet, they are alone. They may feel unable to learn. When put into groups or asked to practice the language with others, they can see that they are not alone in the process of learning a new language

Communicative language teaching integrates reading, writing, and speaking, which can have students practice multiple skills at once. It also uses groups or pairs for activities and tools and technology to create a more individualized learning experience for students, which aids their language learning abilities, such as their fluency in the language.

What is a communicative language teaching example?

An example of communicative language teaching can be an activity that has students discuss their favorite sport. CLT prioritizes the individual needs and interests of students, so having students group together or pair together to discuss their favorite sport can have them practice speaking the new language regarding something that they are passionate about. There are various benefits to CLT, such as it being holistic and engaging. Students who can discuss their favorite things may feel more passionate in speaking to others and out loud instead of speaking about something that is not as engaging to them. CLT is also a learner-centered approach, in which activities are focused on and driven by students instead of teachers.

To sum up, communicative approaches have a great role in teaching english. Using it during the lesson makes the lesson not only effective but also interesting. We can see this in examples such as role playing and various interviews.

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